

GLOBE Observer Eclipse 2023-2024

The NASA Earth Science Education Collaborative focused efforts on GLOBE Observer Eclipse in 2023-2024 to achieve the following objectives:

- Use the annular and total eclipses to engage new and diverse audiences in NASA Earth science with an emphasis on the Sun-Earth connection and Earth's energy budget.
- Engage a wide range of community partners to recruit and support a volunteer community
- Collect cloud, temperature, and land cover data to support student and scientific research associated with eclipses.

GLOBE Observer App Updates

- Added Land Cover observation to site set up
- Improved accessibility and offline functionality
- Translated for Spanish, Portuguese, and French
- Added unique eclipse paths

Eclipse Products

- Resource toolkits for Informal educators, volunteers, and media
- [Landing page](#)
- 9 video explainers in English and Spanish
- 4 handouts
- 2 worksheets, tips for student research
- Signs, presentation, tips for events

Engaging and Supporting Partners

- 25 partners engaged
- 3 partners distributed physical material for NESEC
- 19 partners distributed information and digital resources to their audiences
- NESEC provided GLOBE Eclipse training to 18 partners
- NESEC co-hosted training with 5 partners
- For both eclipses, 64% of all data came from partner teams.

Engaging Volunteers Directly

- 34 presentations to audiences (students, life long learners, scientists, decision makers and public)
- 11 eclipse tabling events (not counting NASA SunSpot events)
- Social media engagement through NASA flagship, NASA Earth, NASA Climate, NASA Espanol, and GLOBE social media platform reach more than 2.2 million
- 48 news articles, 7 NASA features, and 1000 views of media kit

Data Collected

- **60,613** air temperature data points
- **34,345** air temperature data points excluding weather station data
- **761** land cover observations
- **25,400** cloud observations
- **421** new accounts created for October eclipse
- **2,605** new accounts created for April eclipse

Clouds on October 14, 2023

Clouds on April 8, 2024

